

Extended data: data sources used for Narrative Policy Framework (NPF) analysis

The below table presents the data sources used for applying the NPF methodology of the study "Capturing attention: media and institutional narratives on carbon capture, utilisation, and storage in three EU countries", which will be published on Open Research Europe.

The study countries are Denmark, Greece, and Romania.

For Denmark, the following data sources were reviewed:

- Media content: articles and editorials from:
 - The 5 most-circulated national publications at the time of writing (B.T., Politiken, Jyllands-Posten, Berlingske, Ekstra Bladet, Danmarks Radio and TV2)
 - The 4 most-circulated national publications for energy or climate news (Natur & Miljø, Magasinet Teknik & Miljø, Grønt Miljø, Videnskab.dk)
 - The most important national news outlets (Danmarks Radio and TV2)
- Public statements, speeches or press releases from:
 - Public authorities (for example: the Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities, the Danish Council on Climate Change, the City of Copenhagen, Members of Parliament and political parties)
 - The 10 largest emitters from the private sector, based on CO₂ emissions data provided by the ConsenCUS team, as well as the Confederation of Danish Industry (Dansk Industri)
 - NGOs and civil society (such as the Citizen's Assembly, the Youth Climate Council, Noah/Friends of the Earth Denmark, the Danish Society for Nature Conservation, Concito, the Danish Climate Movement, Synergi and the Danish Society of Engineers)
- National agreements, strategies and plans of Denmark (e.g. National Energy and Climate Plan, national climate agreements for energy and industry and other long-term strategies).

For Greece, the following data sources were reviewed:

- Media content: articles and editorials from:
 - The 5 most-circulated national publications at the time of writing (Kathimerini, Ta Nea, Naftemporiki, Efysn, To Vima)
 - Google News
- Public statements speeches or press releases from:
 - Public authorities (for example: the Ministry of Environment, the Ministry of Energy, Members of Parliament)
 - The 10 largest emitters in the private sector, based on CO₂ emissions data provided by the ConsenCUS team, and other relevant companies (EDEY, Energean, Corinth Pipeworks)
 - NGOs and civil society (such as Greenpeace, WWF, The Green Tank)

- National strategies and plans (the National Plan for Energy and Climate, Recovery and Resilience Plan).

For Romania, the following data sources were reviewed:

- Media content: articles and editorials from:
 - The 5 most-circulated national publications at the time of writing (Digi24, Libertatea, Playtech, Adevărul, Observator News)
 - The 5 most-circulated national publications for energy or climate news (E-nergia, Energonomics, Energy Industry Review, Focus Energetic, InvestEnergy),
 - Google News
- Public statements, speeches or press releases from:
 - Public authorities (for example: Ministry of Energy, Ministry of Environment, Members of Parliament)
 - The 10 largest emitters in the private sector, based on CO₂ emissions data provided by the ConsenCUS team
 - NGOs and civil society (such as Greenpeace, Bankwatch, CO₂ Club)
- National strategies and plans of Romania (e.g., National Energy and Climate Plan, long-term energy strategies, Recovery and Resilience Plan).

The data sources were identified in consultation with Danish, Greek, and Romanian experts involved in the ConsenCUS project.

The following keyword combinations were translated into the languages of the three study countries and used as search terms:

- “carbon capture and storage”
- “carbon capture and utilization”
- “carbon capture, utilization and storage”
- “CCS”
- “CCU”
- “CCUS
- “carbon capture”
- “carbon utilization”
- “carbon storage”
- “CO₂ capture/ utilization/storage”
- “carbon dioxide capture/utilization/storage”
- “geoengineering”/ “climate engineering”.